

Nicotinamide Complexes of Some Divalent Metal Ions

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Amides have gained considerable importance as ligands in recent years since in addition to carbonyl group, they have an amide group as a potential donor site. Thus far only complexes of transition and non-transition metals have been isolated in which the carbonyl oxygen is the bonding site excepting one or two cases¹. This aroused our interest to study a number of lactams and amides as ligand. In an earlier communication² we have described complexes of lactams with some divalent metal ions and it was thought worthwhile to study the complexing ability of nicotinamide because of its biological importance and the presence of three bonding sites, i.e. heterocyclic nitrogen, amido, nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Triethoxy acetic acid solution of metal salts were stirred for 2 hr. at 30° and ethanolic solution of nicotinamide in 1 : 2 ratio were added to it. Resulting solutions were refluxed for 30 min. On cooling compounds separated out in some cases, in other cases treatment with ether and allowing the solution to stand overnight resulted in separation of compounds. These were filtered under suction, washed with anhydrous ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo. Metal and halogen or thiocyanate was analysed by standard methods, conductance was measured in $M/1000$ acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal Conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimen using Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on nujol mulls by Perkin-Elmer-21 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in the visible range was measured with $M/100$ (chloroform + amide) solution by Hilger-Watt-Uvispec Spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical data are recorded in Table-1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation are found to be of the composition ML_2X_2 where X is Cl^- , Br^- , NCS^- , NO_3^- and L is nicotinamide. Acetone solution of the complexes have low molar conductance values, i.e. 8-12 mhos (Table-1) indicating non-electrolytic nature. Copper(II) complexes have magnetic moments in the range of 1.7-1.8 BM indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. Magnetic moments of Ni(II) and Co(II) halide complexes are in the range of octahedral moments for these metal ions whereas the nitrate and thiocyanato complexes are those for compounds having a tetrahedral geometry.

The ligand can be bonded to the metal by one or more than one of the three bonding sites. I.R. Spectra of the complexes presently studied, do not show appreciable shift in the C=O stretching frequency, but show considerable shift of the NH asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies (Table 2). This indicates that the ligand is not bonded either through carbonyl oxygen or heterocyclic nitrogen atom. There is lowering of the N-H stretching band due to bonding of the N-atom and probably due to hydrogen bonding. Bonding through the amido nitrogen is the most probable one which has been confirmed by earlier works^{3,4} on iso-nicotinamide, nicotinamide complexes. I.R. spectra of nitrate complexes indicate monodentate nitrate group excepting that of cobalt, from the observed value⁵ of $\nabla\nu$ around 130 cm^{-1} ($\nabla\nu = \nu_4 - \nu_1$ the NO_3^- asymmetric and symmetric stretch). Observed bands due to $\nu(C \equiv N)$ in case of thiocyanato complexes indicated terminally N-bonded thiocyanato groups.

In the solution electronic spectrum of Co(II) halide and nitrate complexes two absorption bands were observed at 21.0 ($\epsilon=19$) and 18.8 ($\epsilon=28$) K.K., the third band was outside the visible region. In case of the thiocyanato complex only one intense band was observed around 16.2 K.K. ($\epsilon=1300$), the other two expected bands being outside the visible range. This indicates a probable octahedral geometry for the halide complexes involving a halogen bridged

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Colour and form	Λ M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% Metal		% Halogen or thiocyanate	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
$CoCl_2(N.A)_2$	130	Pink powder	10	4.8	15.54	15.75	18.72	18.98
$CoBr_2(N.A)_2$	220	-do-	8.6	5.1	12.58	12.71	34.11	34.44
$Co(NO_3)_2(N.A)_2$	145	Orange crystal	11.5	5.0	13.48	13.77	-	-
$Co(NCS)_2(N.A)_2$	165	Blue crystal	10	4.45	13.86	14.06	27.28	27.68
$NiCl_2(N.A)_2$	250 d	Light green powder	8.5	2.9	15.42	15.70	18.72	18.99
$NiBr_2(N.A)_2$	157	-do-	8.5	3.1	12.28	12.69	34.25	34.53
$Ni(NO_3)_2(N.A)_2$	155	Blue crystal	11	3.8	13.34	13.75	-	-
$Ni(NCS)_2(N.A)_2$	158	-do-	8.0	3.9	13.88	14.01	27.34	27.69
$CuCl_2(N.A)_2$	265 d	Light blue powder	8.5	1.83	16.3	16.78	18.32	18.75
$CuBr_2(N.A)_2$	235 d	Light green powder	10.5	1.84	12.85	13.03	41.91	42.19
$Cu(NO_3)_2(N.A)_2$	162	Light blue powder	6.8	1.80	14.25	14.72	-	-
$Cu(NCS)_2(N.A)_2$	175	Green powder	7.5	1.78	14.65	15.00	27.05	27.38
$ZnCl_2(N.A)_2$	140	White crystals	9.5	-	16.82	17.18	18.16	18.65
$ZnBr_2(N.A)_2$	152	-do-	6.4	-	13.68	13.92	33.84	34.03
$Zn(NCS)_2(N.A)_2$	148	-do-	10.8	-	12.98	13.38	23.28	13.74

Infrared Spectra (cm⁻¹)

Table 2

Electronic Spectra in K.K. (ε)

Compounds	Asym. N-H	Sym. N-H	Amide I ν(C=O)	ν(C=N)	ν(C≡N)	ν ₁ NO ₂		ν ₄ NO ₂	
						Sym.	Asym.	Sym.	Asym.
Nicotinamide	3350	3180	1650	1400					
CoCl ₂ (N.A) ₂	3200	3150	1645	1410					
Co(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3300	3140	1645	1410					
Co(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3320	3160	1640	1410	2080	1250	1450		
NiCl ₂ (N.A) ₂ [†]	3310	3140	1650	1390					
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3285	3145	1655	1400		1270	1400		
Ni(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3315	3160	1650	1420	2100				
CuCl ₂ (N.A) ₂	3310	3150	1640	1420					
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3290	3160	1645	1400					
Cu(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3300	3155	1640	1410	2080	1260	1390		
Zn(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3310	3150	1650	1420	2100				

structure, a bidentate nitrate group for nitrate complex and tetrahedral geometry for the thiocyanato complex which is corroborated by the respective magnetic moment values.

Ni(II) halide complexes give rise to three absorption bands, the band positions and intensity being typical of spin free octahedral complexes. Nitrate and thiocyanato complexes are blue in colour giving a single absorption band at 15.0 K.K. (ε=160), the other expected band being outside the visible region. Band intensity, its position and the magnetic moment suggests⁶ a possible tetrahedral environment for these two complexes.

Cu(II) halide complexes have one single broad absorption band around 14.0 K.K. indicating a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure. Though three transitions are expected⁷ as a result of splitting due to Jahn-Teller distortions. More often than not the three transitions appear⁸ in form of a single broad band envelope. Nitrate and thiocyanato complexes give rise to a broad band around 17.0 K.K. (ε=80) suggesting a probable planar structure⁹.

All the zinc complexes reported here have an octahedral stereochemistry on the basis of their analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data.

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Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species. Part. III : *Rhizophoraceae*, a Mangrove Family

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A thorough investigation for secondary metabolites of Sundarban mangroves has been undertaken from the stand point of ecological study^{1,2}. In the present communication, triterpenoids characterised from four mangrove species belonging to four different genera of mangrove family *Rhizophoraceae* are described.

Literature survey did not reveal the presence of any triterpenoid constituents in these four genera. However, the presence of cyanidin chloride and unidentified leucoanthocyanin³ in *B. gymnorrhiza*; brugine alkaloid and its ester^{4,5} in *B. sexangula*; procyanidin⁶, several leucoanthocyanidins⁶, *D. catechin*⁶, leucocyanthoin⁷ in *C. roxburghiana* have been reported.

Plant materials for investigation were collected from Sundarban (West Bengal) in the month of December.

Petroleum extract of leaves of *R. conjugata* was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions by usual procedure¹. Each of the two fractions were then chromatographed, the former one directly and latter after esterification with diazomethane. The acidic portion yielded no triterpenic acid. The result of chromatographic separation of neutral fraction is given below.

First fraction was white crystalline solid, m.p. 166°, [α]_D+117° (C, 0.8); ν_{max} 1700 (carbonyl), 1650 cm⁻¹ (double bond); M.S. m/e 424 (M⁺), 409 (M⁺-CH₃), 218 (retro Diels-Alder fragmentation),